

DEBT STRATEGIES OF EUROPEAN COUNTRIES AND VECTORS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF BEST EXPERIENCE IN THE PRACTICE OF EXTERNAL PUBLIC DEBT MANAGEMENT OF UKRAINE

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Abstract

The policy of external and domestic public debt management in different countries has its own specifics, and its results are not always unambiguous. Thus, the existing recommendations of the International Monetary Fund and the Maastricht criteria prove that the maximum value of public debt to GDP should be no more than 60 %. Exceeding this limit can lead to a deterioration in financial stability, debt sustainability, and ultimately to a technical default of the state. However, the practice of public debt management in many developed countries shows quite opposite trends, as a significant excess of the Maastricht criterion not only does not lead to default, but on the contrary allows countries to accumulate the necessary financial resources to ensure stable economic growth.

Therefore, the study of European debt strategies and their effectiveness is a very important issue, especially given the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic for developing countries. Given the growing external debt dependence of Ukraine as a result of both the war with the Russian Federation and the COVID-19 pandemic, the search for a better experience of European debt policy and consideration of ways to adapt it to domestic realities are discussed in our article.

Based on the analysis of the debt policy of European countries, the expediency of using debt rules, aimed at regulating both the country's debt security and the effectiveness of the use of public borrowing to stimulate economic growth has been proved.

Cluster analysis of debt strategies of some European countries has shown that the high level of dependence on external public debt has a negative impact on economic security in general, because in the event of deteriorating macroeconomic situation, the likelihood of foreign investors selling government securities increases, and in the case of external loans from international financial and credit organizations – the risks of negative impact of burdensome non-financial obligations on the national economy grow.

Keywords: public debt, external public debt, debt policy, debt rule, debt dependence.

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1. Introduction

The slowdown in economic growth due to the negative shocks, associated with the COVID-19 pandemic, raises the issue of studying the issues of public external and domestic debt management. The reduction of state budget revenues and the growth of the budget deficit necessitate the use of external public debt as a tool of macroeconomic policy, which is aimed at overcoming the effects of the pandemic and restoring economic growth. However, the increase in external and domestic debt of the world due to the pandemic leads to an increase in their debt dependence and increased debt risks, which negatively affect economic security.

Based on these positions, the authorities of the vast majority of countries face the task of choosing an effective strategy for public debt management in general and external debt in particular, which requires a thorough empirical study of approaches to debt dependence and efficiency of public borrowing.

Research on public debt management, the impact of debt risks on economic development and economic security of the state, the principles of building debt policy strategies, as well as aspects of external debt dependence are among the main topics in the economic literature. Among the scholars who conducted a thorough professional study of public debt and its relationship to economic growth is Roubini Nouriel [1], who in his work explored the risks of debt crises in the world economy in the post-pandemic period and concluded that prolonged stagflation is inevitable, both in the case of continued soft fiscal and monetary policies and in the case of anti-inflationary measures. According to the scientist [2], governments around the world should resort to monetizing the state budget deficit in order to mitigate the inevitable stagflation and debt crisis.

Noteworthy is the study [3], in which the authors, based on an empirical study of public debt management policy in developed countries with a high debt burden, argue that the policy of increasing the domestic and foreign public debt in Europe during the COVID-19 pandemic is a justified government response to the economic crisis. However, the excessive debt burden, which significantly exceeds the Maastricht criterion of public debt, increases the risks of increasing the vulnerability of the economies of such countries in the event of financial imbalances and economic shocks in the future. Therefore, in order to minimize the negative impact of excessive debt burden on the economy, countries with high debt levels need to return to fiscal discipline and reform to stimulate economic growth.

In a study by Ahlborn M. and Schweickert R. [4], the authors note the dependence of the impact of public debt on economic growth on the economic system and economic structure, dividing countries into three clusters: liberal economic model (Anglo-Saxon countries), continental (major EU members), northern (Scandinavian countries). And from our point of view, the distribution of countries by type of economic system is a good argument, because the traditions of public management in these countries allow different uses of public debt for economic growth.

Scholars Çiftçioğlu S. and Sokhanvar A. [5] studied the impact of external debt on economic growth in 20 countries in Central and Eastern Europe and found a positive impact in only 8 countries that are not post-communist ones. In post-communist countries, the external debt has a negative effect on economic growth, which requires the optimization of the debt and fiscal policy in general in order to activate domestic drivers of economic growth.

The paper [6] considers the practical aspects of the implementation of a public debt management strategy in Central and Eastern Europe and concludes that the success of the strategy depends on the developed primary and secondary markets of government securities and public debt hedging instruments, as well as primary dealers. The author proposes to focus on debt hedging and refinancing of public debt in order to increase its term and reduce the peak burden of costs, associated with servicing external public debt in foreign currency, on the state budget.

Janikowski Ł. [7] emphasizes the need to create a fiscal buffer in the event of deteriorating economic conditions through a strong fiscal policy through compliance with fiscal rules, including the fiscal rule on public debt. However, according to the author, fiscal rules will be effective only if deputies will not be able to change the law overnight, ie draws attention to the need for stability in the context of fiscal rules.

The works of the above authors reflect quite different views on the vectors of the impact of external public debt on economic growth; some of them confirm the positive impact, and others – negative. However, in general, scholars emphasize that the result that an increase in public debt will have a positive impact on economic growth can be achieved only in the case of an effective debt policy and debt strategy based not only on fiscal rules but also on the targeted use of public borrowing to finance economic recovery (as in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic) or to stimulate economic growth.

The **aim** is to assess and systematize the debt strategies of European countries to implement best practices in the realities of Ukraine's debt policy in the post-pandemic economic recovery.

2. Methods

The following methods were used in the study:

- analysis and synthesis – in the study of scientific literature and determination of debt strategies of European countries and the effects of public debt on economic growth;
- methods of cluster analysis – for the division of European countries into clusters according to the level of debt risk and debt dependence.
- economic and statistical analysis and comparison – in the study of the effects of domestic and foreign public debt on economic growth;
- economic-mathematical method – in the study of correlations between indicators of external and domestic debt of European countries and the dynamics of GDP and the dynamics of GDP per capita;
- generalization – for the formation of scientific-theoretical and practical recommendations for optimizing the debt strategies of European countries in general and Ukraine in particular.

3. Results

The spread of coronavirus in Europe had extremely detrimental effects on the economies of European countries, as none of the countries was ready to fight the unknown disease, which led to the introduction of strict quarantine restrictions for 2–3 months. The result was the closure of production, catering, transport, which in turn led to a decline in business activity and falling GDP. Thus, according to Eurostat, the fall in GDP of the European Union due to the COVID-19 pandemic is estimated at 7.4 %, and the overall budget deficit at 10.1 % in 2020 [7, 8]. Such negative trends in the economic dynamics are due to the fact that the economies of the EU are interconnected, and the simultaneous introduction of quarantine restrictions has had a negative impact on trade relations and labor migration.

In order to overcome the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic and increase funding for the medical sector, the European Commission has approved a € 750 billion financial assistance package, which has led to an increase in the EU budget deficit [9].

At the same time, each European country has chosen its own strategy to overcome the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, in which one of the main instruments of macroeconomic policy was public debt, as evidenced by the analytical data in **Table 1**.

Table 1

Growth rates of public domestic and external debt of some European countries in 2018–2020, %

Growth rates of domestic and external public debt by country	2018	2019	2020	Growth rates of domestic and external public debt by country	2018	2019	2020
Austria PDD*	-4.88	-2.74	5.27	Luxembourg PDD	-0.87	5.24	5.60
Austria PED**	-0.44	-2.74	20.22	Luxembourg PED	-0.87	18.84	23.97
Belgium PDD	1.17	9.54	10.23	Malta PDD	-1.81	-1.20	17.74
Belgium PED	1.17	-6.76	10.23	Malta PED	7.59	16.68	46.45
Bulgaria PDD	-5.70	1.41	36.62	Netherlands PDD	-3.46	-4.33	13.87
Bulgaria PED	-5.70	-2.64	11.73	Netherlands PED	-3.46	-0.24	4.69
Croatia PDD	4.09	10.04	10.88	Norway PDD	-12.67	-7.99	16.71
Croatia PED	-4.39	-11.83	10.88	Norway PED	6.86	-7.99	16.71
Cyprus PDD	44.36	-14.26	6.62	Poland PDD	4.02	14.26	38.41
Cyprus PED	6.09	2.44	21.43	Poland PED	-3.98	-10.23	-5.15
Czechia PDD	7.36	1.55	33.79	Portugal PDD	5.14	-1.76	14.97
Czechia PED	-12.52	1.55	-1.16	Portugal PED	-2.96	2.25	1.96
Denmark PDD	39.75	4.32	14.66	Romania PDD	11.93	14.42	19.14
Denmark PED	-45.65	-5.75	60.73	Romania PED	7.54	5.59	45.57
Estonia PDD	8.15	-20.34	108.78	Slovakia PDD	1.86	2.01	30.38
Estonia PED	-8.46	34.60	108.78	Slovakia PED	1.86	2.01	15.46
Finland PDD	19.73	2.37	18.00	Slovenia PDD	16.40	1.06	23.95
Finland PED	-8.07	2.37	13.12	Slovenia PED	-6.46	-3.12	14.04
France PDD	8.64	-3.03	13.60	Spain PDD	-2.83	-6.05	24.28
France PED	-3.66	9.35	9.15	Spain PED	9.79	10.32	1.64
Germany PDD	1.54	-2.67	19.54	Sweden GDP	-1.95	1.32	-0.45
Germany PED	-6.28	1.32	5.95	Sweden PDD	-5.52	-3.14	16.71
Hungary PDD	3.94	4.02	13.79	Sweden PED	-0.11	-23.32	16.71
Hungary PED	-0.45	-4.73	8.80	UK PDD	1.12	6.35	11.93
Ireland PDD	2.30	-0.81	17.51	UK PED	1.12	3.62	8.98
Ireland PED	2.30	-0.81	-0.30	Ukraine PDD	6.25	10.65	0.95
Italy PDD	6.73	-3.06	9.92	Ukraine PED	3.01	-3.02	12.38
Italy PED	-7.37	11.69	0.11	Belarus PDD	-7.85	3.87	-19.68
Latvia PDD	-7.81	3.98	43.89	Belarus PED	4.54	4.18	-2.98
Latvia PED	7.17	3.98	2.64	Russian Federation PDD	30.77	21.56	-9.49
Lithuania PDD	-3.94	-1.97	64.49	Russian Federation PED	6.63	13.74	-8.59
Lithuania PED	-8.64	20.73	21.21				

Note: *PDD – public domestic debt; **PED – public external debt; Source [10]

The data in **Table 1** show that 19 of the 31 countries analyzed have chosen a strategy to increase the domestic public debt in order to overcome the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, as the growth rate of the domestic public debt in 2020 is significantly higher than in 2019. The highest growth rates of the domestic public debt are observed in Estonia (108.78 %), Lithuania (64.49 %), Latvia (64.49 %), Poland (38.41 %), Bulgaria (36.62 %), and the Czech Republic (33.79 %), Slovakia (30.38 %), Spain (24.28 %) and Slovenia (23.95 %). Analyzing the debt policy of these countries, the question arises whether such a strategy is a planned decision, whether it arose under the influence of coincidence of circumstances, related to the impossibility of attracting external public debt due to low sovereign rating? However, analyzing the debt policy of other European countries, we note that countries, such as Romania and Ukraine (where the level of economic development is lower than in the above countries), managed to increase the external public debt by 45.57 % and 12.38 %, respectively.

Thus, the analysis of the data, presented in **Table 1**, gives grounds to conclude that most European countries have chosen a debt strategy, focused on the domestic debt market. In our opinion, such a strategy is justified not only during the COVID-19 pandemic or other economic crises, but also during the implementation of optimistic scenarios of economic development. After all, the debt strategy, focused on the domestic market of public borrowing, has, in our opinion, three significant advantages over the debt strategy, focused on the foreign market. First, domestic public debt can be attracted in the national currency, which greatly simplifies its servicing. Secondly, in states where the domestic public debt prevails over the external one, there is a one-time possibility, in case of force majeure, to carry out mutual debt write-off. However, it should be noted, that this possibility should be one-time, in order to prevent various political speculations in the future. Third, in case of force majeure, the central bank can be involved in the financing of domestic public debt as a counterparty of last resort. Such a mechanism among European countries was used by France in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, whose central bank owns 18 % of domestic government bonds.

In addition, it should be noted, that less developed countries, such as Ukraine and Belarus, in order to effectively use the debt strategy, focused on the domestic market, must organize the work of their own stock market. In this case, these countries will be able to attract not only financial corporations to finance the public debt, but also non-financial corporations and households, following the example of European countries, such as Malta, Hungary, Portugal, Ireland, Italy and others.

As for the debt strategy, focused on the foreign market, which was chosen by such countries as Denmark (60.73 %), Romania (45.57 %), Luxembourg (23.97 %), Cyprus (21.43 %), Austria (20.22 %), Ukraine (12.38 %), Croatia (10.88 %), Belgium (10.23 %), it can also be effective if the targeted use of the external public debt to stimulate economic growth. However, such a strategy carries higher risks than the strategy, focused on the domestic market, because in times of crisis, foreign investors can quickly sell foreign government bonds and, thus, reduce the level of debt security. In addition, it should be emphasized, that the structure of external public debt by type of creditor is also important for its debt security. Thus, if one of the external creditors is an international financial institution, despite the relatively low interest rate on the loan, the terms of the agreement may include political obligations, which provide for reforms that are not always in the national interest. For example, the ban on the use of protective import duties, the ban on restricting the export of raw materials, the ban on the adoption of legislation on the localization of public procurement, which was used in relation to Ukraine during the signing of memoranda with the International Monetary Fund

In this case, one of the strategic goals of the world in the field of debt policy is to limit debt dependence on international financial institutions and their non-financial requirements. The implementation of the state's foreign debt policy should be based on the need to increase the volume of public borrowing on a market basis in international money and capital markets. Such a strategy is relevant for Ukraine today, but for its implementation it is necessary to take measures to increase the sovereign rating by carrying out reforms that will improve the overall investment and business climate in the country.

In addition to external debt dependence, which can be measured by the share of external public debt in gross public debt, one of the debt risks is the excessive debt burden on the economy, which is measured by the ratio of public debt to gross domestic product. The threshold value of the ratio of public debt to GDP is justified in the IMF guidelines and the EU Maastricht Treaty and is 60 % of GDP. This criterion is used as a debt rule or budget constraint in various countries in Europe and the world.

Given the availability of statistics on the share of external public debt in gross public debt and the ratio of public debt to GDP, we will conduct a cluster analysis of 31 European countries in order to grade them according to debt risk and public debt management strategies (Fig. 1). At the same time, it should be noted, that in order to determine the direction of the debt strategy for a long period of time, statistical data for the last eleven years (2010–2020) were selected for calculation.

Fig. 1. Cluster analysis of some European countries by the level of debt risk in 2010–2020.
Source: [10, 11]

Thus, as evidenced by **Fig. 1**, the European countries can be divided into three clusters in terms of debt risk. The first cluster includes those countries, in which the level of gross public debt relative to GDP is close to the threshold of 60 %, and the share of external public debt is more than 45 %, namely: Finland, Slovenia, Ukraine, Slovakia, Poland, the Netherlands, Belarus, Lithuania, Latvia. In other words, countries have been complying with the ratio of gross public debt to GDP for the last eleven years, but their economy and financial stability depend on the behavior of external investors, who own half of the public debt.

The second cluster includes countries with a low level of debt dependence – Malta, Norway, Romania, Sweden, Denmark, the Czech Republic, the Russian Federation, Luxembourg, Estonia, Bulgaria. The second cluster reflects countries with a ratio of gross public debt to GDP below 40 %, while the share of external public debt also does not exceed 40 %. In our opinion, such a debt policy strategy is the most justified, as it minimizes the impact of debt shocks on the development of the national economy, which can be a good example for implementation into domestic realities.

The third cluster includes countries with a high level of debt dependence, in which the ratio of gross public debt to GDP exceeds the threshold of 60 %, and the share of external public debt is approaching 50 % – Portugal, Italy, United Kingdom, Croatia, Hungary, Germany, Austria, Cyprus, Ireland, Spain, France, Belgium.

The debt strategy of the third cluster countries is the most risky, as the ratio of public debt to GDP significantly exceeds the Maastricht criterion of 60 % (Fig. 2). Maim Maastricht criterion: public debt/GDR=60 %

Fig. 2. Results of compliance with the Maastricht criterion of public debt by some European countries in 2010–2020. Source: [11].

The results of the analysis of compliance with European Maastricht criteria of public debt during 2010–2020 allow us to determine their debt strategy, which in the third cluster is high-risk and provides debt financing of economic development.

In order to reduce the levels of debt risk and debt burden on the economies of European countries within the European Union, the European Commission applies supranational fiscal rules, which provide for the following components:

- the general budget must be balanced or in surplus;
- the above provision is considered to be complied with if the annual structural balance is aimed at achieving the medium-term objective, set out in the EU Stability and Growth Pact – limiting the structural deficit to 0.5 % of GDP;
- countries may temporarily derogate from their medium-term commitments to achieve their objectives in exceptional circumstances;
- if the debt-to-GDP ratio is below 60 % and the risks to long-term financial stability are low, the lower limit of the structural budget deficit may not exceed 1 % of GDP;
- in case of significant deviations from the medium-term objectives, the correction mechanism should work automatically, in particular, the binding party to the contract should take appropriate measures within a certain period of time [12].

However, in practice, we observe non-compliance with these rules by the third cluster countries over the past eleven years, which indicates a low level of effectiveness of fiscal rules in terms of compliance with the criteria for the ratio of public debt to GDP at 60 %.

At the same time, the countries of the first and second clusters adhere to the Maastricht criterion, using not only the rules of the European Union, but also their own fiscal rules and fiscal restrictions. A reference example in this area can be considered the example of Poland, where the debt rule is enshrined in the Constitution of the country and sets the debt threshold at 60 % of GDP.

At the same time, the Law on Public Finances set three prudential thresholds for the ratio of public debt to GDP (50 %, 55 % and 60 %), according to which prudential and corrective procedures are applied in three ranges:

- the first range – the ratio of public debt to GDP exceeds 50 % and is less than 55 %;
- the second range – the ratio of public debt to GDP exceeds 55 % and is less than 60 %;
- the third range – the ratio of public debt to GDP is equal to or exceeds 60 % [7].

Achieving the indicators of each range obliges the Council of Ministers to apply a number of restrictions and prohibitions to the budgets of the state and local governments and the introduction of corrective instruments.

In 2013, the first range of Poland's public debt-to-GDP ratio was abolished, and the other two ranges are actively used in the implementation of public debt management policy. Thus, if the ratio of public debt to GDP exceeds 55 % but less than 60 %, the first adjustment procedure is launched, which includes tools to counteract this unfavorable trend, affecting both central and local finances. First of all, this procedure obliges the Council of Ministers to impose restrictions on the content of the draft budget act for the next year. In case of launching the first corrective procedure, the Council of Ministers was obliged to prepare a draft budget act, which does not provide for a state budget deficit or provides for the level of revenues and expenditures of the state budget in the amount that ensures compliance with the debt-to-GDP ratio of 60 % for the end of the next year.

Moreover, this procedure provides for a number of measures to limit and review the financial resources, spent from the state budget. These include: suspension of salary increases for employees of budgetary institutions; valorization of pensions at the maximum level, corresponding to the increase in prices for consumer goods and services, announced by the Central Statistical Office for the previous financial year; ban on granting loans and credits from the state budget, except for installments of loans and credits, granted in previous years; suspension of the increase of expenditures in subdivisions, bodies of state power at a level higher than in the state administration; revision of state budget expenditures, financed by external loans, and revision of long-term programs by the Council of Ministers; revision of current regulations of the Council of Ministers in order to make legal decisions that affect the level of state budget revenues, including the application of tax rates on goods and services; reduction of the target subsidy from the state budget for vocational and social rehabilitation and employment; introduction of restrictions on new obligations of public administration bodies to increase investment expenditures.

The procedure for applying the most restrictive instruments arises when public debt reaches or exceeds 60 % of GDP. In this case, the second procedure of public debt adjustment begins, which provides for the ban on determining the budget deficit, limiting wage growth, indexation of pensions, the ban on new loans and credits from the state budget, revision of budget expenditures, restrictions on new commitments investing, revision of regulations, affecting the level of revenues and expenditures of the state budget. In turn, with regard to the finances of local self-government units, an absolute procedure for balancing the budget was established, in particular, the expenditures of the local self-government budget, included in the budget resolution for the next year, cannot be higher than budget revenues. Another restriction is set for the units of the State Treasury and is the prohibition of them to provide new sureties and guarantees. The ban takes effect on the 7th day after the publication of information that the public debt exceeds the constitutional threshold. The purpose of the ban is to counteract the increase in contingent liabilities, which include obligations and guarantees, provided by units of the State Treasury, so as not to impair the financial confidence of the state as a borrower [13].

Both procedures for adjusting the Poland's public debt require the Council of Ministers to submit a rehabilitation program to the Sejm, with the difference that if the constitutional debt threshold is exceeded, a deadline has been set for its submission (one month from the date of declaring the size and ratio of the public debt to GDP).

This approach to the implementation of the debt rule and debt policy of the Polish government as a whole not only prevents the debt threshold from being exceeded, but also promotes fiscal discipline in general, as legal restrictions minimize political speculation in the field of budget

expenditures and increase personal and departmental responsibility of the Government and the Central Bank to attract and use the domestic public debt.

In our opinion, given the peculiarities of European debt policy and the active use of public debt to stimulate economic growth, the view of fiscal rules in general and debt rules in particular should be changed, as the accumulation of old debts against the background of shortening economic cycles makes it impossible to meet Maastricht or other similar criteria.

In this context, in our opinion, the debt rule of the United Kingdom is effective, which provides for the attraction of the external public borrowing solely to finance public development programs. This rule requires the United Kingdom Government to make targeted and efficient use of the external public debt, which in turn affects the share of external debt in the gross debt, which has not exceeded 40 % over the last eleven years. The introduction of such a rule in Ukraine can be one of the steps to reduce the level of external debt dependence [12].

In Germany, the fiscal rule limits the net public borrowing to the level of investment, with the exception of periods of “general economic imbalance.” Linking public borrowing to net investment is, in our view, a good incentive to build effective fiscal-budget and debt policies, as the need to find new resources to stimulate economic growth requires the Government to seek, first and foremost, ways to increase investment, and then attracting the public debt.

Thus, the current debt strategies of the countries of the three clusters we have selected should be based not on quantitative indicators of debt dependence reduction or compliance with a certain amount of domestic and external public debt, but on qualitative indicators of the use of public borrowing. Such indicators may be the coefficients of correlation of the dynamics of domestic and external public debt with the dynamics of GDP and the dynamics of GDP per capita or indicators of conversion of the public debt into capital expenditures of the state budget and so on.

The analysis of correlations between indicators of domestic and external public debt and the dynamics of GDP and GDP per capita allows to draw a conclusion about the level of efficiency of public borrowing use for stimulation of economic growth (**Table 2**).

Table 2

The results of the correlation analysis of the dynamics of domestic and external public debt, as well as GDP and GDP per capita of some European countries in 2010–2020

No.	Indicators of GDP and GDP per capita in some European countries	Public debt/GDP ratio, %	Domestic public debt, bil euro	External public debt, bil euro
1	2	3	4	5
1	Austria GDP	-0.6452	-0.4998	0.7998
	Austria GDP per capita	-0.6779	-0.4844	0.7774
2	Belgium GDP	-0.0717	0.8152	0.7004
	Belgium GDP per capita	-0.1285	0.7927	0.6735
3	Bulgaria GDP	0.4168	0.6786	0.8530
	Bulgaria GDP per capita	0.4315	0.6892	0.8610
4	Croatia GDP	0.0176	0.6691	0.1747
	Croatia GDP per capita	0.1152	0.7398	0.2502
5	Cyprus GDP	0.0176	0.6691	0.1747
	Cyprus GDP per capita	0.1152	0.7398	0.2502
6	Czechia GDP	-0.7927	0.0319	0.7462
	Czechia GDP per capita	-0.7972	0.0225	0.7478
7	Denmark GDP	-0.7634	0.2309	-0.2239
	Denmark GDP per capita	-0.7622	0.2342	-0.2265
8	Estonia GDP	0.4813	0.6374	0.7266
	Estonia GDP per capita	0.4770	0.6290	0.7221
9	Finland GDP	0.4813	0.6374	0.7266
	Finland GDP per capita	0.4770	0.6290	0.7221
10	France GDP	0.6703	0.9072	0.6565
	France GDP per capita	0.6148	0.8802	0.6082

Continuation of the Table 2

1	2	3	4	5
11	Germany GDP	-0.9625	0.5869	-0.6881
	Germany GDP per capita	-0.9625	0.5648	-0.6674
12	Hungary GDP	-0.7317	0.9423	-0.9490
	Hungary GDP per capita	-0.7298	0.9464	-0.9518
13	Ireland GDP	-0.9065	0.7006	0.2440
	Ireland GDP per capita	-0.9124	0.6833	0.2456
14	Italy GDP	-0.9065	0.7006	0.2440
	Italy GDP per capita	-0.9124	0.6833	0.2456
15	Latvia GDP	-0.7019	0.7217	0.8329
	Latvia GDP per capita	-0.6858	0.7410	0.8313
16	Lithuania GDP	0.2027	0.7641	0.8718
	Lithuania GDP per capita	0.1959	0.7634	0.8672
17	Luxembourg GDP	0.4340	-0.4377	0.9440
	Luxembourg GDP per capita	0.4003	-0.4465	0.9367
18	Malta GDP	-0.9513	0.6720	0.9061
	Malta GDP per capita	-0.9696	0.6432	0.8574
19	Netherlands GDP	-0.8426	0.7595	-0.9332
	Netherlands GDP per capita	-0.8582	0.7404	-0.9354
20	Norway GDP	-0.6937	0.1318	-0.3971
	Norway GDP per capita	-0.5775	-0.1111	-0.5352
21	Poland GDP	-0.4625	0.5656	0.4129
	Poland GDP per capita	-0.4604	0.5670	0.4126
22	Portugal GDP	-0.1150	0.8983	-0.4911
	Portugal GDP per capita	-0.0518	0.9130	-0.4389
23	Romania GDP	0.4320	0.5856	0.9096
	Romania GDP per capita	0.4370	0.5890	0.9113
24	Slovakia GDP	0.4646	0.6679	0.7440
	Slovakia GDP per capita	0.4672	0.6747	0.7394
25	Slovenia GDP	0.4039	0.9001	0.5242
	Slovenia GDP per capita	0.3928	0.8876	0.5175
26	Spain GDP	0.2655	0.4221	0.6836
	Spain GDP per capita	0.2435	0.3991	0.6660
27	Sweden GDP	0.1608	0.8446	-0.2048
	Sweden GDP per capita	0.2971	0.6350	0.0499
28	UK GDP	0.4185	0.7490	0.7377
	UK GDP per capita	0.3015	0.6635	0.6416
29	Ukraine GDP	-0.7588	0.2899	-0.0380
	Ukraine GDP per capita	-0.6216	0.5070	0.1937
30	Russian Federation GDP	-0.4102	0.0581	-0.0145
	Russian Federation GDP per capita	-0.4568	0.0118	-0.0778
31	Belarus GDP	-0.5870	-0.3081	-0.1785
	Belarus GDP per capita	-0.5831	-0.3103	-0.1713

Source: [10, 11].

According to the data in **Table 2**, in 24 of 31 countries, the dynamics of domestic public debt has a high level of correlation with the dynamics of GDP and the dynamics of GDP per capita. In 16 countries, the dynamics of external public debt also has a high level of correlation with the

dynamics of GDP and the dynamics of GDP per capita. In total, public debt in the form of a macroeconomic policy instrument is used by 27 European countries in addition to Denmark, Ukraine, Belarus and the Russian Federation. External public debt in countries, such as Germany, Hungary, the Netherlands and Norway, has a negative impact on economic growth.

Thus, the effective use of public borrowing to stimulate economic growth eliminates the risks of a debt strategy, because increasing GDP by financing infrastructure and innovation projects, supporting value-added production can increase state budget revenues and create the necessary financial cushion to smoothly service the domestic and external public debt. At the same time, the development of the infrastructure of the national economy and the development of industry is the key to improving the investment climate, which has a positive effect on the sovereign rating of the state and, consequently, its ability to attract the external debt on acceptable economic conditions.

Promising areas of research in this area are the study of the experience of debt policy of developed countries in terms of ensuring the effective conversion of external public borrowing into economic growth.

4. Conclusion

Each European country has an individual debt strategy, but its effectiveness depends not on compliance with quantitative fiscal rules and budgetary constraints, but on the qualitative conversion of public borrowing into economic development. Modern fiscal and debt rules, which are aimed at minimizing debt risks and limiting the debt burden, cannot be effective due to the reduction of economic cycles and unbalanced development of the world economy, so their main role should be to stimulate the use of public borrowing for economic growth. Therefore, it is expedient to introduce such a debt rule, which provides for the implementation of the program-target method of attracting the external public debt.

In addition, as shown by the cluster analysis of the debt strategies of some European countries, the high level of dependence on external public debt has a negative impact on economic security in general, because in the event of deteriorating macroeconomic situation, the likelihood of foreign investors selling government securities increases, and in the case of attracting external loans from international financial and credit organizations – risks of negative impact of burdensome non-financial obligations on the national economy grow.

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